

Ultrasonic Study of the Elastic Constants of Some Ancient and Mediaeval Indian Coins

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Using the ultrasonic pulse technique, elastic constants like the bulk modulus, shear modulus, Young modulus and Poisson's ratio, have been determined for Indian coins belonging to various periods of history. The results are discussed in the light of chemical composition, spectrographic analysis and the microstructural observations.

FOR the last several years, the senior author has been interested in the archaeological studies of Indian antiquities. Prakash and Rawat¹ published a monograph giving a detailed account of their results on the chemical analysis of some of the objects of interest found at Kausambi. Later, Prakash and Singh² reported their results on the chemical, spectrographical, microstructural studies of a large number of Indian coins from the earliest times. In a recent paper, Prakash and Murthy³ have published their results on the heterogeneity of ancient Indian coins. In the present paper, an attempt has been made to calculate several elastic constants of the metals used in coinage during different historical periods using the ultrasonic pulse technique.

Experimental

The coin from the hoard is first cleansed by the usual methods and polished. For the ultrasonic pulse technique, the coin is suspended in an ordinary rectangular brass cell containing water, having two quartz crystals (serving as transducer and receiver) parallel to each other and fixed on the opposite walls. The technique uses a synchronizing generator (SG), time-based generator (TBG), wide band amplifier (WBA), detector (DA) and output amplifier (OPA) connected in sequence (Fig. 1). The oscillograph (OSC) and the output stage (OPS) are also

Fig. 1. Pulse technique.

shown in the figure. As the coin is rotated from the original direction (i.e. at right angles to the direction of the incoming ultrasonic waves) within 90°, two critical angles (θ_1 and θ_2) are obtained.

When the coin is perpendicular to the direction of longitudinal waves, the waves are transmitted completely as longitudinal waves. As the angle between the direction of longitudinal waves and the coin is decreased from 90°, a point comes when there is no transmission of the longitudinal waves. This is our first critical angle (θ_1). The coin is continued to rotate till a second critical angle (θ_2) is obtained at which shear waves in the coin also cease to be transmitted. For the position beyond this critical angle, there will be no transmission of ultrasonic waves (provided the coin possesses a certain minimum size). Using these two critical angles, we have been able to calculate certain elastic constants for the metals of the coins.

Elasticity constants from the critical angles :

If V_L is the velocity of longitudinal waves in water (which is 1470 m/sec at 27°), V'_L the velocity of the longitudinal waves in the coin, and V'_S is the velocity of the shear waves in the coin, then the critical angles θ_1 and θ_2 are related as :

$$\begin{aligned} V'_L &= V_L / \sin \theta_1 \\ V'_S &= V_L / \sin \theta_2 \end{aligned}$$

The bulk modulus K and Poisson's ratio σ are given by the expressions :

$$\begin{aligned} K &= V'_L / V'_S \\ \sigma &= (K^2 - 2) / 2(K - 1) \end{aligned}$$

The Young modulus (E) and the shear modulus (F) are related to the Poisson's ratio and the density (ρ) of the coin as well as to each other by the following two expressions :

$$\begin{aligned} E &= 2(1 + \sigma) F \\ F &= (V'_S)^2 \cdot \rho \end{aligned}$$

From Snell's law we know that

$$\sin \theta / V_L \pm \sin \theta_L / V'_L = \sin \theta_S / V'_S$$

where θ is the angle of incidence of longitudinal waves at the surface of the solid, and θ_L and θ_S are the angles of transmission of the longitudinal and shear waves in the solid, respectively.

Before starting our work on the old and ancient coins of India we studied, for reference, some modern coins for their elastic constants by the

pulse technique and Table 1 gives these results. The subsequent tables give our results on the punch-marked coins (*karshapanas*) belonging to about 300-200 B.C., Indo-Sasanian coins (550-700 A.D.), *Kushana* copper coins (25-425 A.D.), Oudh coins (1700 A.D.), Kashmir coins (100 A.D.), Yaudheya coins; *Bahamani* coins (1358-1482 A.D.), coins of Shershah (1539-45 A.D.) and Islamshah (1545-53 A.D.) Mughal coins of Akbar (1556-1605), Jehangir (1605-27), Shahjahan (1627-58) and Aurangzeb (1658-1707), and some other miscellaneous coins (*Kausambi*, *Taxila*, *Zemisa*, *Chola* and *Lanky-bull*). The chemical and spectrographic analyses of these coins have been reported by us earlier².

Discussion

Perhaps, the earliest work on ancient coins was started by Klapproth near about 1815⁴, followed by Bibra (1869) on bronzes and copper alloys of ancient times⁵. Since 1922, various attempts have been made by the Archaeological Survey of India to carry-out scientific investigations on ancient metal objects, including those found at the capital sites of Mohenjo-daro and Harappa. Analyses of ancient Indian bronzes were reported by C. H. Desch to the Sumerian Copper Committee and many of these were incorporated in Sir John H. Marshall's complete report on the archaeological investigation and M. S. Vats report on Harappa excavations⁷.

TABLE 1—BULK MODULUS AND POISSON'S RATIO OF SOME MODERN COINS

Coin	θ_1 mean	θ_2 mean	V_L' m/sec	V_S' m/sec	K	σ
5 RF Franc, (1945)	11°30'	32°15'	7373.3	2754.8	2.672	0.4189
Penny, British, (1936)	18 22.5	47 45	4663	1986	2.3479	0.3316
Arab, (1900)	18 52.5	40 7.5	4544	2281	1.9921	0.3316
Heliana, (1952)	12 55	32 22.5	6576	2745	2.3956	0.3945
Franc, (1943)	13 7.5	34 45 2	6474	2579	2.5103	0.4057
Shilling, British, (1953)	17 00	35 22.5	5028	3862	1.3019	0.2195
Paisa, Indian, (1966)	18 7.5	35 37.5	4725	2524	1.8720	0.3004

TABLE 2—ELASTIC CONSTANTS OF SOME PUNCH-MARKED COINS (300-200 B.C.)

(Rectangular; figures of animals, wheel etc. on reverse.)

	Weight (g)	Thickness (mm)	Density (ρ)	θ_1	θ_2	V_L' m/sec	V_S' m/sec	K	σ	$E \times 10^{11}$	$F \times 10^{11}$
1.	3.240	0.29	6.77	24°15'	47°45'	3579	1986	1.8021	0.2775	6.83	2.670
2.	3.260	0.28	6.64	12 52.5	34 45	6597	2579	2.5580	0.4098	12.45	4.416
3.	3.215	0.26	6.89	15 52.5	48 15	5374	1970	2.7279	0.4223	7.61	2.674

TABLE 3—ELASTIC CONSTANTS OF INDO-SASANIAN COINS (550-700 A.D.)

	Weight (g)	Thickness (mm)	Density (ρ)	θ_1	θ_2	V_L' m/sec	V_S' m/sec	K	σ	$E \times 10^{11}$	$F \times 10^{11}$
1.	3.550	0.36	6.53	17° 7.5'	45°00'	4992	2079	2.4012	0.3951	7.87	2.822
2.	3.716	0.38	6.84	21 22.5	44 30	4033	2097	1.9232	0.3147	7.91	3.008

TABLE 4—ELASTIC CONSTANTS OF *Kushana* COPPER COINS (25-425 A.D.) AND OUDH COINS (1700 A.D.)

(circular with the portrait of the king on the obverse and a figure of certain deity on the reverse)

	Weight (g)	Thickness (mm)	Density (ρ)	θ_1	θ_2	V_L' m/sec	V_S' m/sec	K	σ	$E \times 10^{11}$	$F \times 10^{11}$
<i>Kushana</i>											
1.	14.905	0.35	8.61	16°45'	38° 7.5'	5101	2381	2.1424	0.3607	13.28	4.881
2.	13.995	0.28	8.22	19 15	34 45	4459	2579	1.7290	0.2487	13.63	5.459
3.	12.335	0.35	7.79	17 52.5	42 00	4789	2197	2.1798	0.3667	10.28	3.760
4.	15.995	0.40	7.95	16 52.5	45 00	5064	2079	2.4358	0.3986	9.61	3.436
5.	14.897	0.30	8.17	18 30	43 45	4633	2126	2.1792	0.3666	10.09	3.693
<i>Oudh</i>											
1.	10.465	0.41	10.43	41 7.5	56 45	2235	1758	1.2713	0.3114	4.44	3.224
2.	10.723	0.39	9.89	16 00	41 22.5	5333	2224	2.3979	0.3947	13.65	4.892
3.	11.06	0.41	10.52	19 15	61 37.5	4459	1671	2.6685	0.4183	8.33	2.937
<i>Kashmir</i>											
1.	7.612	0.41	7.53	17 30	34 30	4888	2595	1.8836	0.3038	13.22	5.071
2.	6.852	0.40	7.86	19 00	36 00	4515	2501	1.8053	0.2787	12.57	4.916
<i>Yaudheya</i>											
1.	11.190	0.41	9.55	15 30	35 30	5501	2531	2.1734	0.3657	16.71	6.118
2.	5.154	0.40	9.38	17 75	41 45	4992	2208	2.2609	0.3784	12.61	4.573

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TABLE 5—ELASTIC CONSTANTS OF COINS OF BAHAMANI KINGS, SHERSHAH AND MUGHAL EMPERORS (1358 TO 1707 A.D.)

Bahamani Kings : Coins 1 and 2 : Bin Mahmud Shah (1358-73) ; Coin 3 : Humayum Shah (1457-61) ; Coin 4 : Muhammad III (1463-82) ; Coins 5 and 6 : Shershah (1539-45) ; Coins 7 and 8 : Islamshah (1545-53) ;
Mughal coins : Coins 9-12 : Akbar (1556-605) ; Coin 13 : Jehangir (1605-27),
Coins 14 and 15 : Shahjahan (1627-58), and Coins 16-21 : Aurangzeb (1658-1707).
(Circular ; King's portrait on the obverse and the name of the mint on the reverse)

	Weight (g)	Thickness (mm)	Density	θ_1	θ_2	V_L'	V_S'	K	σ	$E \times 10^{11}$	$F \times 10^{11}$
Bahamani											
1.	15.650	0.58	7.97	17°30'	38°52.5'	4889	2342	2.0875	0.3511	11.81	4.372
2.	16.357	0.50	8.46	17 7.5	37 45	4992	2401	2.0791	0.3495	13.16	4.877
3.	16.990	0.60	8.37	16 30	37 52.5	5176	2394	2.1621	0.3639	13.08	4.797
4.	19.735	0.60	8.35	18 15	39 22.5	4694	2317	2.0259	0.3389	12.01	4.483
Shershah											
5.	20.370	0.61	8.41	16 52.5	37 52.5	5064	2394	2.1153	0.3561	13.07	4.820
6.	20.145	0.70	8.51	17 7.5	37 52.5	4992	2394	2.0852	0.3507	13.17	4.877
Islamshah											
7.	20.490	0.70	8.42	16 15	37 15	5253	2429	2.1626	0.3640	13.55	4.968
8.	11.230	0.39	10.18	21 45	58 00	3967	1733	2.2891	0.3821	8.45	3.057
Akbar											
9.	19.070	0.50	8.37	19 22.5	40 15	4431	2275	1.9477	0.3210	11.45	4.332
10.	20.005	0.40	8.36	18 15	38 00	4694	2388	1.9657	0.3254	12.64	4.767
11.	18.730	0.50	8.37	19 22.5	40 15	4431	2275	1.9477	0.3210	11.45	4.332
12.	11.287	0.39	10.33	19 15	59 00	4459	1715	2.6000	0.4132	8.59	3.038
Jehangir											
13.	11.225	0.30	10.37	20 7.5	58 22.5	4272	1726	2.4751	0.4025	8.67	3.089
Shahjahan											
14.	11.230	0.34	10.36	24 22.5	53 22.5	3562	1832	1.9443	0.3202	9.18	3.477
15.	10.085	0.32	10.43	19 7.5	52 30	4487	1853	2.4215	0.3972	10.01	3.581
Aurangzeb											
16.	20.770	0.66	8.29	17 30	41 15	4889	2230	2.1924	0.3687	11.29	4.123
17.	20.301	0.62	8.46	14 52.5	36 45	5726	2457	2.3305	0.3872	14.17	5.107
18.	20.765	0.60	8.40	17 15	38 30	4957	2361	2.0995	0.3532	12.67	4.682
19.	20.680	0.69	8.44	17 53.5	39 45	4789	2299	2.0831	0.3503	12.05	4.461
20.	11.325	0.32	10.43	16 30	50 00	5176	1919	3.0099	0.4380	11.05	3.841
21.	11.261	0.33	10.39	20 37.5	59 45	4173	1702	2.4518	0.4002	8.43	3.010

TABLE 6—ELASTIC CONSTANTS OF MISCELLANEOUS OLD COINS

Weight (g)	Thickness (mm)	Density (ρ)	θ_1	θ_2	V_L' m/sec	V_S' m/sec	K	σ	$E \times 10^{11}$	$F \times 10^{11}$
<i>Kausambi</i>										
5.640	0.32	6.63	16°45'	36°15'	5104	2487	3.0522	0.3440	11.02	4.101
<i>Taxila</i>										
9.704	0.42	7.83	17 30	36 15	4956	2487	1.9968	0.3326	12.90	4.842
<i>Zemisis</i>										
4.690	0.36	7.90	19 15	39 52	4461	2293	1.9454	0.3205	10.97	4.154
<i>Chola</i>										
8.279	0.39	8.12	20 00	42 22	4298	2183	1.9688	0.3261	10.26	3.870
<i>Lanky-bull</i>										
5.675	0.37	6.54	17 80	35 45	4936	2515	1.9825	0.3293	11.00	4.137

Prof. E. R. Caley's work on Greek and Roman coins evoked our interest in the archaeological chemistry of ancient Indian coins, and our results have been incorporated in a comprehensive monograph². Birbal Sahni published in 1945 a memoir on the techniques of casting coins in ancient India on behalf of the Numismatic Society of India³. Most of the techniques utilised for the study of the ancient coins are destructive in the sense that a few

grains of the material has to be knocked out of the coin, and hence the museums are always reluctant in sparing their valuable collections. In search of a non-destructive method, we have taken recourse to the ultrasonic pulse technique. The earliest coins studied in the present project were the punch-marked coins of about 200 B. C., consisting of a metal with density (6.64-6.89) and thickness near about 0.28 mm. The most representative specimens are available

from Taxila hoard, Bodenayakanur hoard and Paila hoard, and also from Andhra Pradesh. Among the commonest coins of ancient India are the unscribed cast copper pieces, square, round or rectangular in shape, having symbols in relief (like a tree in railing, hollow cross, crescented hill or elephant). They are usually found on sites which yield punch-marked silver coins. From our analysis, we find that the composition of the punch-marked rectangular silver coins in terms of silver and copper is

	Coin 1	Coin 2	Coin 3	Coin 4
Ag	65.97	88.46	91.72	20.4
Cu	32.21	9.60	7.32	77.23

The punch-marked copper coins we studied had the following compositions: Cu, 89-91; Pb, 5.94; Sn, 0.77-2.27; Fe, 1.44-5.1%. Punch-marked copper coins are much rarer than the punch-marked silver coins.

We have earlier given² the detailed chemical compositions and the results of the spectrographic analysis and microstructures of the coins. In this paper, we present our results on the elastic properties of the coins. For reference, we are giving here the bulkmodulus (K), Poisson's ratio (σ), Young modulus (E) and shear modulus (F) for the pure coinage metals.

	E $\times 10^{11}$	F $\times 10^{11}$	σ	K	Density
Copper	12.98	4.83	0.343	1.378	8.9
Silver	8.27	3.03	0.367	1.036	10.5
Lead	1.61	0.559	0.44	0.458	11.34
Iron, soft	21.14	8.16	0.293	1.698	—
Iron, cast	15.23	6.0	0.27	1.095	7.9
Tin	4.99	1.84	0.357	0.582	5.77 (α) 7.29 (β)
Zinc	10.84	4.34	0.249	0.72	7.1
Brass (Cu 30, Zn 70)	10.06	3.73	0.350	1.118	—

Indo-Sasanian coins are circular, with the average composition Ag, 15; Cu, 82; Pb, 0.84%. Some of them are poorer in silver, as low as 4.5%. Their elastic constants are given in Table 3. *Kushana* coins are of a wide period (25-425 A.D.); they are circular, with a royal figure on the obverse and a deity on the reverse. Their density is of the range 8.17-8.61. Analysis of a large number of *Kushana* coins with densities ranging between 7.79 and 8.61, and the chemical composition: Cu, 96-99 with small quantities of sulphur (0.69-1.23); iron from traces to 4.79% and with traces of nickel and calcium have been carried out. The elastic constants tabulated in Table 4 are compatible with the microstructure which consists of polyhedral grains of a single solid solution, showing lots of twin crystals. Under the microscope, some of the grains appear dark brown and some light brown. This

difference in shade was discussed in an earlier publication³. The metal is quite homogenized indicating that either the coin was cold-worked and reheated to a high temperature where a fairly good amount of recrystallization took place, or it was worked at a quite high temperature.

The next coins we studied were three centuries old (1700 A.D.), belonging to the rulers of Oudh. These coins are circular with density 9.8-10.4. Their elastic constants are also given in Table 4. This table also includes the measurements on Kashmir coins of an early period (100 A.D.) and the Yaudheya coins. The Yaudheya are known for their past history. The *sutras* of *Panini* (5th century B.C.) mention of them. They constituted a sturdy race of warriors. *Sahni* referred to their coins and minting moulds, and these coins have also been described by *Swami Omananda* in his monograph⁹. We could get two Yaudheya coins for our present study with densities 9.55 and 9.38.

The other coins that we have studied belong to the Muslim period with considerably developed technique of minting and metallurgy, the Bahamani coins of Karnataka (1358-1482 A.D.), *Shershah* coins and the coins of Mughal emperors. In the last table, we have included our measurements on some miscellaneous coins we could procure, belonging to the sites of *Kausambi* and *Taxila*, a coin of *Zemesis*, and of *Chola* family and a *Lanky-bull* coin. The last one has been so nicknamed from its having a mythical animal (partly a horse and partly a bull) on the obverse, and a tree in railing, a wheel, arched hill, or a swastika on the reverse^{2,3}. The coin has small amount of tin and a good quantity of lead which could preserve it against the hazards of environments. Our analysis gave for the coin the following composition: Sn, 8.53-9.62; Cu, 89; Pb, 1.02-1.17; Fe, 0.32-0.41; Ni, 0.19-0.26; S, 0.24-0.27%.

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References

1. S. PRAKASH and N. S. RAWAT, "Chemical Study of some Indian Archaeological Antiquities", Bombay, 1965.
2. S. PRAKASH and R. SINGH, "Coinage in Ancient India", New Delhi, 1968.
3. S. PRAKASH and J. V. G. MURTHY, *Vijnana Pari. Anu. Patrika*, 1980, 23, 207.
4. E. R. CALEY, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1949, 26, 242.
5. E. VON BIBRA, "Die Bronzen und Kupferlegierungen der Alten und Aeltesten Voelker", Erlangen, 1869.
6. JOHN H. MARSHALL, "Mohenjo-Daro and Indus Civilisation", London, 1931, Vol. 2, p. 574.
7. M. S. VATS, "Excavations at Harappa", Delhi, 1940, Vol. 1, p. 378.
8. B. SAHNI, *Memoirs Numis. Soc. of India*, 1945.
9. OMANANDA SARASVATI, "Ancient Mints of India" (Hindi), 1970.